

FACTORS AFFECTING PEOPLE'S INTENTION TO BUY FUNCTIONAL FOODS – A CASE STUDY IN HANOI CITY

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Abstract

To examine the variables influencing individuals' inclination to purchase functional food in Hanoi, the research team surveyed 366 customers living in Hanoi who purchased and used functional foods from a reputable company specializing in the production of functional foods in Hanoi city. Researchers used the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991) to build a research model and used SMARTPLS software to process the collected data. Research results show that all three factors considered have an impact. Among them, the factor "Attitude towards functional foods" strongly impacts Hanoi people's intention to buy functional products, with an influence of 0.446. Next is the factor "Perceived behavioural control" with an influence level of 0.308; Finally, the factor "Subjective Norms" with an influence level of 0.177. Following the analytical findings, the study team engaged in many talks aimed at enticing consumers to develop an interest in, purchase, and use functional food.

Keywords: Functional Foods, Intention to Purchase Functional Foods, Influencing Factors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Functional foods are important in our daily lives, especially in an ever-changing and ever-evolving society. Functional foods have many applications, such as supporting the prevention of nutritional deficiencies, supporting disease prevention, and promoting growth and development in children. Other areas where functional foods can bring positive effects are skin care, sports, and the endocrine system. (Minh Thuy, 2022)

According to statistics from the Vietnam Association of Functional Foods (GAFF), the number of people using functional foods is increasing to 1/5 of the population. The functional food market in Vietnam currently has great development potential. However, there are still worrying challenges for functional foods.

Realizing the urgency of developing the functional food market in Vietnam, the research team conducted the project "Factors affecting people's intention to purchase functional foods - Case study at businesses in Hanoi". The case study of a functional food manufacturing enterprise is an enterprise specializing in producing functional foods. It has over 12 years of experience and

has introduced many different types of functional products to the market. Through research, the research team evaluated the influence of three factors: "Attitude towards functional foods"; "Perceived behavioural control", and "Subjective Norms" and then proposed directions and solutions to attract people to care about and use functional foods, contributing to the development of the functional food market in Vietnam in the coming years.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Functional foods

The Japanese Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare defines: "Food for Specified Health Uses (FOSHU) refers to foods containing ingredients with functions for health and officially approved to claim its physiological effects on the human body"

Canada's Department of Agriculture considers functional foods to be "foods enhanced with bioactive ingredients and which have demonstrated health benefits, such as probiotic yoghurt or bread and pasta with added pea fibre" (Investone, 2024)

The Vietnam Functional Food Association defines: "Functional Food as a product that supports the functions of organs in the body, with or without nutritional effects, gives the body comfort, increases resistance, and reduces the risk and harmful effects of the disease (Investone, 2024)

Thus, it can be understood that functional foods are a form of food that nourishes and compensates for substances lacking in our body to help the body become healthier.

2.2. Some research models on behavioural intentions

2.2.1. Theory of reasoned action

The theory of reasoned action (TRA) model was built by Fishbein and Ajzen in 1975. According to the model, Behavioral Intention leads to behaviour and intention is determined by individual attitudes toward the behaviour, along with the influence of subjective norms surrounding the performance of those behaviours (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975).

Source: Fishbein and Ajzen (1975)

Figure 1: Theory of reasoned action

- 1) *Consumer's attitude toward performing the behaviour*. Each individual's attitude is measured by the consumer's personal beliefs and evaluations of the results of that behaviour. When there is trust in the product, consumers tend to promote the intention to use the business's product (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975)
- 2) *Consumers' subjective standards*. Consumers are influenced by the attitudes of those around them, such as friends and relatives involved in using the product, and the consumer's motivation towards performing the behaviour desired by those around them. (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975).

2.2.2. Theory of planned behaviour model

Ajzen (1991) developed the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) based on the original theory of reasoned action (TRA). The TPB includes the addition of perceived behavioral control, as well as the two factors of attitude and subjective norm, which influence consumers' behavioural intention.

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is a conceptual framework that elucidates human behavior by considering their deliberate purpose to carry out a certain activity. The TPB model suggests that an individual's inclination to engage in a certain behavior is controlled by three primary factors: Attitude, Subjective norms, and Perceived behavioral control. These characteristics are interconnected and may be used to anticipate a person's desire to engage in a certain behavior. This intention then directly impacts the actual behavior. The TPB model enhances comprehension of the influence of psychological and social variables on human behavior. (Ajzen, 1991)

Source: Ajzen, 1991

Figure 2: Model of the theory of planned behaviour – TPB

Attitude toward a behaviour can be understood as people's feelings toward a product or service and their evaluation of that behaviour, which can be positive or negative but is based on their perception of the expected results (Ajzen, 1991). Subjective norm refers to an individual's perception of social pressure to perform a behaviour. This correlates with the ability to feel pressure from those around you and the perception of social criticism or approval (Ajzen, 1991). Perceived behavioural control includes self-control and self-awareness. Self-control refers to individuals' beliefs about external influences that may influence their behaviour. Self-

awareness is an individual's assessment of his or her ability to perform that behaviour (Ajzen, 1991).

2.3. Propose a model and research hypothesis

From research and theoretical systems based on the TPB theoretical model of planned behaviour, the research team proposes the following research model:

Source: Compiled and proposed by the research team

Figure 3: Expected research model

Research hypothesis

Hypothesis H1: *"Attitude towards functional foods" has a positive impact on the intention to purchase functional foods of Hanoi people.*

Hypothesis H2: *"Subjective norm" has a positive impact on the intention to buy functional foods of Hanoi people*

Hypothesis H3: *"Perceived behavioral control" has a positive impact on Hanoi people's intention to purchase functional foods.*

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Data collection methods

Based on theory and an overview of research on factors affecting behavioural Intention, Factors (independent variables) included in the model include: "Perceived behavioural control", "Subjective norms", and "Students' attitudes toward culinary tourism in Hai Phong". The survey form is built on a 5-point Likert scale with the following indicators:

- 1) *Totally disagree*
- 2) *Disagree*
- 3) *Normal*
- 4) *Agree*
- 5) *Totally agree*

Following the development of the survey questionnaire, the research team carried out a random pilot survey of 15 clients in Hanoi. Initial survey findings indicate that views align with the variables used in the model.

Given the constraints of time and money, the author used a convenience sampling strategy for the survey. The sample size was selected based on the guidelines established by Comrey and Lee (1992) and also took into account the recommendations of Hoang Trong & Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc (2005). To do factor analysis with 20 observed variables, a minimum of 100 observed samples is required, assuming a ratio of 5 samples per parameter. The studied participants are clients residing in Hanoi who have bought and used functional meals from specialized enterprises in Hanoi city. In order to assure the stability of the effect, the study team opted to distribute a total of 400 votes, as this amount allows for the collection of a sufficient number of observation samples. The questionnaire was delivered to the survey subjects by submitting online via the link:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSc4U5NnpD9WRPpkQiAJIPQW0cGVt1QGQP-CI-0_VdiILNB0sVg/viewform. The number of ballots received was 366, which the research team used as the database for analysis.

3.2. Data processing method

A quantitative research methodology was used to analyze the research data obtained from the survey. The structural regression equation is characterized by a generic form:

$$YD = a*KS + b*CQ + c*TD$$

SMARTPLS software is used to test hypotheses and evaluate the impact of factors.

The collected data was processed with the two main steps:

Step 1: Evaluating Measurement Model

Evaluating measurement model based on examining values of reliability, quality of observed variable, Convergence, and discriminant

- Testing the quality of observed variables (Outer Loadings)

Outer loadings of observable variables are indicators that measure the strength of the relationship between observed variables and latent variables (also known as proxy variables). In SMARTPLS, the outer loadings may be calculated by taking the square root of the absolute value of the R^2 linear regression from the latent variables to the sub-observed variables. According to Hair et al. (2016), the outer loadings should be greater than or equal to 0.708 so that the observed variables can be considered quality.

- Evaluating Reliability

Reliability is evaluated through SMARTPLS using two main indicators, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). Chin (1998) claims that in exploratory research, CR must be over 0.6. For confirmed studies, the 0.7 threshold is the appropriate level of CR (Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013).

- Testing Convergence

The evaluation of convergence on SMARTPLS is determined by the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) (Hoang & Triet, 2024). Hock and Ringle (2010) argue that a scale is considered to have reached a convergence value when the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) achieves a threshold of 0.5 or more. A level of 0.5 (50%) indicates that, on average, the hidden variable will account for at least 50% of the variability in each sub-observed variable. Convergence is assessed by determining whether the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is greater than or equal to 0.5, as stated by Hock and Ringle (2010).

- Testing Discriminant Validity

The discriminant value is used to assess if a research variable really exhibits distinctiveness from other research variables inside the model. In order to assess the discriminant validity, Sarstedt et al. (2014) proposed two criteria: cross-loadings and the Fornell and Larcker (1981) assessment.

SMARTPLS preferred a threshold of 0.85 in the evaluation.

- Testing Multicollinearity

The author of this research employs a scale that is connected to multicollinearity and serves as a variance magnification factor (VIF). When the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) readings are equal to or more than 5, it indicates that there are very high levels of multicollinearity. On the other hand, if the VIF indications are less than 5, it means that the model does not have multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2016).

Step 2: Evaluating Structural Model

- Evaluating impactful relationships

To assess the effect linkages, use the findings from Bootstrap analysis. The analysis primarily relies on two key factors: (1) the Original Sample, which is the normalized impact factor, and (2) the P Values, which indicate the significant level relative to a threshold of 0.05.

- Original Sample
- Sample Mean
- Standard Deviation
- T Statistics
- P Values

Assessing the level of interpretation of the independent variable for the dependent variable using the R^2 coefficient (R square): The PLS Algorithm analysis results will be employed to assess the R^2 coefficient. Furthermore, the team determined the distance value and average value of each factor in order to assess the influence of each factor. The researchers also determined the response threshold within which the average score falls.

According to Hoang et al. (2024), distance value = (Maximum - Minimum) / n = 0.8

Evaluation thresholds based on average score value:

- + 1,00 – 1,80: Totally disagree
- + 1,81 – 2,60: Disagree
- + 2,61 – 3,40: Normal
- + 3,41 – 4,20: Agree
- + 4,21 – 5,00: Totally agree

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Description of the research sample

The number of questionnaires was collected from 366 customers living in Hanoi who purchased and used functional foods from a business specializing in producing functional foods in Hanoi city, including 168 female customers (billion) (45.9%) and 198 male customers (54.1%). Because the survey process followed the convenience sampling method, the number of female customers was more interested and willing to answer the questionnaire, so there was a difference in the gender of the survey participants.

Figure 4: Gender of survey participants

Source: Survey results of the research team

Out of the 366 surveyed clients, 44 individuals had an income of less than 5 million VND per month, which is 12% of the total. There are 62 individuals, making up 16.9% of the total, who earn between 5 million and 10 million VND per month. The number of individuals earning between 10 million and 15 million VND per month is 69, accounting for 18.9%. Additionally, 105 individuals, representing 28.7%, have an income ranging from 15 million to 20 million VND per month. Lastly, there are 86 individuals earning over 20 million VND per month, making up 23.5% of the total. Therefore, it is evident that the majority of the consumers polled had a substantial income above 5 million VND per month. Notably, there are 86 individuals who earn more than 20 million VND each month.

Figure 5: Income level of surveyed subjects

Source: Survey results

4.2. Inspection results

4.2.1. Results of assessing the quality of observed variables in the measurement model

4.2.1.1. Check the quality of observed variables

The quality of observed variables is assessed through the outer loadings. In the first PLS-SEM algorithm test, the outer loading coefficient shows that the observed variables KS4 and YD5 have an Outer loading coefficient < 0.7 , so they are not qualified to ensure the quality of the observed variables; these two variables are removed from the model and 2nd PLS-SEM algorithm test. The results of the 2nd test, the quality of observed variables affecting people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi, are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Outer loadings of factors affecting people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi

	CQ	KS	TD	YD
CQ 1	0.763			
CQ 2	0.816			
CQ 3	0.815			
CQ 4	0.858			
CQ 5	0.817			
KS 1		0.848		
KS 2		0.885		
KS 3		0.873		
TD1			0.702	
TD 2			0.770	
TD 3			0.714	
TD 4			0.719	
TD 5			0.749	
TD 6			0.741	
YD 1				0.822
YD 2				0.865
YD 3				0.885
YD 4				0.851

Source: Testing results of the research team

Results from Table 1 show that the outer loadings of all total variable correlation coefficients of observed variables affecting people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi are > 0.7 (Hair et al., 2016), showing that the observed variables are meaningful, meeting quality conditions to test the next steps.

4.2.1.2. Test the reliability of the scale

Evaluate the reliability of the scale of factors affecting people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi on PLS-SEM through two main indices: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR).

Table 2: Reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) and composite reliability (Composite Reliability)

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
CQ	0.873	0.875	0.908	0.663
KS	0.838	0.848	0.902	0.755
TD	0.828	0.836	0.874	0.537
YD	0.878	0.880	0.916	0.733

Source: Testing results of the research team

According to Table 2, after analyzing and testing the reliability using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the factor, the results are: the factor "Subjective Norms" (CQ) reached 0.873, "Perceived behavioural control" (KS) reached 0.838; "Attitude towards functional foods" (TD) reached 0.828; "Intention to buy functional foods of people in Hanoi (YD) reached 0.878. Thus, all scales satisfy the condition > 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012) and do not violate any rules for eliminating variables, so no variables are eliminated and are acceptable in terms of reliability.

The Composite Reliability (CR) of all observed variables is also > 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988) (Table 2). Therefore, the scale is reliable, has analytical significance and is used in subsequent factor analysis.

4.2.1.3. Convergence

The data analysis results in Table 2 indicate that the average variance extracted (AVE) for the factor "Subjective Norms" (CQ) is 0.663, for "Perceived behavioral control" (HV) is 0.755, for "Attitude towards functional foods" (TD) is 0.537, and for "Intention to buy functional foods of people in Hanoi" (YD) is 0.733. The Average Variance Extracted of all variables is more than 0.5, as stated by Hock and Ringle (2010). This indicates that the model fulfills the convergence requirements.

4.2.1.4. Discriminant Validity and multicollinearity assessment

The results in Table 3 of the Fornell-Larcker index of the model research factors affecting people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi. The factors included in the model ensure discrimination because all AVE square root values on the diagonal are higher than their off-diagonal values.

Table 3: Fornell-Larcker criteria of the research model

	CQ	KS	TD	YD
CQ	0.814			
KS	0.211	0.869		
TD	0.332	0.169	0.733	
YD	0.667	0.350	0.302	0.856

Source: Testing results of the research team

Multicollinearity assessment

The test results show that the Inner VIF index assessing multicollinearity between latent variables is < 3, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity phenomenon in the impact relationship.

Table 4: Inner VIF index

	VIF
CQ -> YD	1.156
KS -> YD	1,059
TD -> YD	1.137

Source: Testing results of the research team

4.2.2. Results of assessing the level of influence using the structural model

4.2.2.1. Evaluate influence relationships

The relationship and level of influence of factors affecting people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi on SMARTPLS are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 6: Impact relationship of factors influencing people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi

Source: Testing results using SMARTPLS by the research team

Influence relationships are shown in Table 6. Accordingly, only two factors, "Subjective Norms" and "Perceived Behavioral Control", are related to the factor "Intent to buy functional foods of people in Hanoi". Specifically:

Subjective norms have a positively correlated impact on people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi ($t = 14.707$; $P \text{ value} < 0.05$) with an impact level of 0.600; *Hypothesis H2 is accepted*. Perceived behavioural control has a positively correlated impact on people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi ($t = 4.870$; $P \text{ value} < 0.05$) with an impact level of 0.212; *Hypothesis H3 is accepted*. The relationship between the factor "Students' attitude towards culinary tourism in Hai Phong" and "intention to buy functional foods of people in Hanoi" is not statistically significant enough to conclude due to the price. $P \text{ Values} = 0.113 > 0.05$; *Hypothesis H1 is rejected*

Table 6: Path Coefficient of the structural model (Path Coefficient)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CQ -> YD	0.600	0.597	0.041	14,707	0.000
KS -> YD	0.212	0.211	0.044	4,870	0.000
TD -> YD	0.067	0.072	0.043	1,584	0.113

Source: Testing results using SMARTPLS by the research team

The test results in Table 6 show that with a reliability of 95 %, the factor "Subjective Norms" (CCQ) has the strongest influence on people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi with an influence level of 0.60; Next is the factor "Perceived behavioural control" (KS) with an influence level of 0.212. From the test results, the regression equation is presented as follows:

$$YD = 0.600 * CQ + 0.212 * KS$$

4.2.2.2. Evaluate the overall coefficient to determine R² (R square)

The results of the PLS Algorithm analysis give the value R², reflecting the level of explanation of the independent variable for the dependent variable. R index² measures the overall coefficient of determination (R-square value), which is an index to measure the degree of model fit of the data (the model's explanatory power). According to Hair et al. (2010), R-square values are suggested at 0.75, 0.50 or 0.25.

Table 7. R-value summary table²

	R-square	R-square adjusted
YD	0.494	0.490

Source: Testing results of the research team

The data in Table 7 shows that the adjusted R² for the representative factor "Intention to buy functional foods of people in Hanoi" is 0.490, so the independent variables explain 49% of the variation (variance) of the dependent variable intention to buy functional foods of people in Hanoi, the remaining 51% is due to systematic errors, factors that are not statistically significant and from other factors outside the model.

4.2.2.3. Reliability index rating (SRMR)

The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is an index indicating the adequacy of a research model. According to Hu & Bentler (1999), typically, a well-fitting model will have an SRMR value of less than 0.08

Table 8: Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) Reliability Index

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.056	0.056

Source: Testing results of the research team

According to the findings, the SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual) in Table 8 of the research model is 0.056, which is less than 0.08. Therefore, this model is considered suitable for data analysis.

4.2.3. Descriptive statistical results

Figure 7: The average value of the factor scale "Subjective Norm" (CCQ)

Source: Survey results

The descriptive statistical results in Figure 4 show that the scale value of the observed variables is in the range of 3.7 to 3.9 points, i.e. in the range of agreement with the opinion. Particularly, the observed variable "I advise family members to buy functional foods" (YD3) reached an average value of 3.88 and "I intend to buy functional foods" (YD1) reached an average value of 3.83, showing that Respondents highly agree with these opinions; Next is the observed variable "Will buy functional foods in the near future" (YD2)" reaching a value of 3.79 and the observed variable, "I advise my friends to buy functional foods" (YD4) reaching an average value of 3.776, are all within the threshold of agreement; The observed variable "I advise my colleagues to buy functional foods" (YD5) has an average value of 3.768, still at the agreed level. This shows that most of the customers surveyed have the intention and need to buy functional foods in the near future.

Figure 8: The average value of the factor scale "Perceived behavioural control."

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The descriptive statistical results in Figure 5 show that all observed variables have average values within the threshold of agreement. The observed variable "I have full freedom to decide on the use of functional foods (KS4)" has an average value of 4.06, showing that customers are pretty independent in purchasing and using functional foods. However, the results of the outer loading test showed that the observed variable KS4 was eliminated because it was not reliable enough.

The observed variables "I am confident in using functional foods" (KS1) and "I know reliable places where I can buy functional foods" both have an average score above 3.8, and the observed variable "I can afford it." finances to buy functional foods" has an average score of 3.798, so the scale values of these variables are all within the threshold of agreement with survey opinions.

Figure 9: The average value of the factor scale "Subjective Norm" (CCQ)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The observed variables of the "Subjective Norms" factor all have an average score at the "Agree" threshold, in which the observed variables "My family (parents, siblings...) I think should buy functional foods" reached the average value is 3.784, the highest among the five observed variables for this factor.

5. DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Test results show that, among the factors included in the model, with 95% confidence, the "Subjective Norms" factor has the strongest influence on people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi with The effect level is 0.60, which is significant. When a customer's "Subjective Norm" increases by 1 unit, the intention to buy functional foods increases by 0.6 units. This is a fairly high level of influence and proves the role of people around and the mass media in having a strong impact on people's intention to buy functional foods.

Next is the factor "Perceived behavioral control" (HV), with an influence on people's intention to buy functional foods in Hanoi of 0.212, meaning when customers' perceived behavioural control increases by 1 unit, the intention to buy functional foods increases by 0.212 units. The factor "Attitude towards functional foods" is not statistically significant enough to consider the relationship affecting the intention to buy functional foods of people in Hanoi. The reason may be that the sample size is not large enough or that the responses of the surveyed people are not really focused. Hopefully, further research will solve this problem.

Descriptive statistics also show results similar to the test results. Most of the customers surveyed have the intention and desire to buy functional foods in the near future. All opinions agree that when customers are propagated and understand the uses of functional foods, are encouraged by people around them, are aware of their financial capabilities, and understand functional foods and Supply addresses, it will influence the intention to purchase functional foods, thereby leading to purchasing and usage behaviour. Thus, the impact of communication is very important, thereby conveying specific information and uses of functional foods to customers, encouraging customers to use them, and allowing customers to have the intention to buy.

Based on the research results, the research team has the following recommendations.

- Strengthen advertising strategies for functional foods. Traditional media channels such as newspapers, magazines, and television are used to deliver messages about the reputation and quality of functional foods. At the same time, take advantage of the potential of social networks by creating attractive advertising content and sharing on platforms such as Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube to effectively reach audiences. In addition, you can use the LinkedIn channel, which is an effective channel for sharing information about functional foods and reviews from experts and creating relationships with partners and specialists.
- Take advantage of certifications and assessments from government agencies and reputable organizations in the medical industry to confirm the quality and safety of products, thereby informing customers. Provide information about independent clinical trials and research to demonstrate the effectiveness and safety of the product.

- Take advantage of collaboration and partnership opportunities with healthcare organizations, medical professionals and government agencies to ensure that product messaging is delivered accurately and reliably.
- Organize exchange events and seminars or experience-sharing sessions with actual product users; Share detailed information about the production process, origin of raw materials, and product quality control steps. Create opportunities for potential customers to meet and talk with people who have experienced and trust the product, thereby increasing trust and purchasing decisions.
- Provide clear and detailed information about prices, as well as promotions and special offers through media channels so customers can choose products that suit their budget.
- Provide information about genuine dietary supplement points of sale, build and maintain a list of verified and trustworthy points of sale on the company's website, with detailed information on addresses and Products available at each store.

Encourage customers to share reviews and comments on points of sale to create trust and confidence in the community.

6. CONCLUSION

This study examines three factors (independent variables) that affect Hanoi people's intention to purchase functional foods. Research results show that only two factors, "Subjective Norms" and "Perceived Behavioral Control", have a relationship with the factor "Intention to buy functional foods". Among them, the factor "Subjective Norms" has the strongest impact on the intention to buy functional foods. Next is the factor "Perceived behavioral control" that affects the intention to buy functional foods. In addition, there is not enough statistical significance to evaluate the relationship between the factors "Attitude towards functional foods" and "Intention to purchase functional foods of Hanoi people". The reason may be that the sample size is not large enough or the responses of the surveyed people are not really focused; this is a suggestion for further research. Based on the results of the analysis, the research team has a number of discussions to attract consumers to pay more attention and buy and use functional foods.

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